

Green Furniture concept

Sustainable design for public interior areas

Seamless, winding and wooden public furniture and lamps improving interior acoustics based on 4 cornerstones : Chemical Awareness, Design & Resources, Reforestation and Post Sales Responsibility

Highlights of innovative features

- The furniture is highly configurable and adaptable to users needs.
- Building Information Modelling BIM data are provided to architects for an easy handling when choosing products for projects.
- The use of up- and recycled raw materials includes steel, aluminium and ocean plastic.
- Product-as-a-Service business models, leasing and buyback conditions foster the circularity of the products.
- For every furniture sold a tree is planted.

Seamless' Seating means room for more people when needed and the possibility of designing grand furniture configurations in scale with large spaces. Configurations that can take any creative formation, follow the lines of the building and lead the flow of people. 'Acoustic Lighting' means lighting designed to provide outstanding visual and acoustic spheres. 'Sustainable' is our story.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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